

What Did the Deceased Want to Say?

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Abstract	Original Research Article
<p>For the study, a request to conduct a forensic linguistic examination was presented to an author. A subject matter of a dispute was a will which was drawn up by the testator K., who was a citizen of Russia, but lived permanently in Italy, and was equally fluent in Russian, English and Italian. A dispute lied in the uncertainty that arose in the interpretation of a phrase recorded in a will.</p> <p>This article is devoted to the study of lexical meaning of the word “Europe”, which during the court hearing revealed disagreement among the heirs. During the study, various methods of linguistic analysis were used, including a survey. In addition, during the study, a search was made for the context in which this word was used using the language Corpora of the English and Russian languages, and its analysis was carried out.</p> <p>The purpose of the study is to comply with the court’s request responsibly, which an author took very seriously. Our mission was to answer the question to whom the testator really wanted to bequeath the property located in Europe.</p> <p>We have at our disposal a wide variety of multiple lexicographical dictionaries, however, when conducting a study requested by the court: “What did an author mean in this text?”, a forensic linguist needs to turn not only to the interpretation of a word recorded in the dictionary, but also to carry out more in-depth analysis of an author’s context and intent.</p> <p>The meaning of each word described in modern sources has limited semantics, since it is considered statically. A person, as a native speaker, does not turn to a dictionary to study the meaning of a word before using it. It is a common situation when a word is used in a completely different meaning than that recorded in the dictionary. This gap between language and thinking can lead to controversial situations, one of which will be discussed in this article. Through a comprehensive experimental study to determine the meaning of the word “Europe”, we hope to be able to come closer to understanding the true intention contained in the testator’s will.</p> <p>Keywords: Linguistic Examination, Connotation, Word Meaning, Language Corpus, Survey, Europe.</p>	

INTRODUCTION

The systemic meaning of a word, recorded in the explanatory dictionaries, is created by lexicographers based on minimizing the characteristics included in this meaning.

To discover the true meaning of the sense contained in a word or a phrase, it is necessary to carry out an in-depth psycholinguistic study, which consists of several stages. At the beginning of the study, it is required to arrange all semantic components that actualize a single word/phrase in the mind of

a particular native speaker, in conjunction with nuclear and peripheral components.

A copy of a will, endorsed with an apostille and translated into Russian, was presented for the study. A will was drawn up in Italian on five A4 sheets by the testator K. (a citizen of the Russian Federation), certified by the notary public A. in the notarial office of Italy.

The object of the study is a will, the intention of the testator K., who is equally fluent in both Italian and Russian, wants to dispose of his property after his death, and this will is

recorded by the notary public. The speech in the text of a will is written, indirect (implicit), that is, a will of the testator was recorded by the notary public A. according to K.

After K.'s death, a dispute arose between the heirs regarding the true intent of the testator, contained in the phrase: *"I dispose exclusively of the property located in Europe, to bequeath to the children from my first marriage."* Well, what is "Europe", and what countries does it include in the minds of the testator K.? Does this concept include both Italy and Russia? Or just Italy? Let's consider this case in more detail.

Study

To be able to follow an author's thread of thought more fully, we will divide the study into three stages.

1. *What is the interpretation of the lexeme "Europe" in various Russian and foreign sources?*

According to V.P. Glukhov: "The semantic meaning of a text or its fragment (paragraph, sentence period and phrase) is based on the meanings of the language units - words, grammatical points (morphemes), syntactic structures (and intonational structures in case of a spoken text)" (Glukhov, 2007). For the same reason, according to S.S. Gusev: "dictionaries are important sources of information that serve to determine the presence/absence of a particular meaning in a text, as well as grammar that describes the meaning of grammatical forms, syntactic and intonational structures" (Gusev, 2008).

However, when conducting forensic linguistic study, experts need to take into account the important fact that lexicographic collections and dictionaries record exclusively the language units and its basic meanings. Nevertheless, a forensic linguist should not reduce the content of the meaning of a text or its fragment only to the meanings of the language units included in it, since this expert error leads to fatal consequences, namely, to an unjust decision. Below we'll list the reasons why the dictionary meaning of a word may not be identical to a word used in the speech by an individual communicator:

1. In addition to the prescribed dictionary meaning, the contextual meaning of a word also contains the additional information about a real object or phenomenon of reality. Besides, a person's consciousness contains a number of conventional views, which he associates with a given word and its connotation in a particular culture, which, together with generally accepted associations about the designated object (background knowledge), form a completely new conceptual framework.

2. The content of the meaning of a text or sentence, including the entire set of morphemes, word meanings, intonational and syntactic structures, in most cases has an additional meaning which a sentence (text fragment) constructed in a specific way introduces into the structure of communicative interaction. For example, the presence of a certain intonation affects the intention in the sentence: "What are you saying?"

When analyzing the language units, an adequate

understanding of communication involves taking into account the totality of not only the purely linguistic environment (intralinguistic context), but also the entire set of the actual conditions in which an act of communication takes place (Hennig, 1975).

According to G.V. Kolshansky: "The task of this and similar linguistic studies with such starting positions in accordance with the presented concept should be to adjust a specific "language effect", try to find the adjustment coefficient that would remove its own linguistic point, and thus, adjust the relationship of a language to reality" (Kolshansky, 2010). And one of the ways of such adjustment can be considered as context, subtext and other points that will be analyzed during the study in order to try to understand what a testator wanted to say. An author also used a survey as a method for this study.

A feature of existing verbal signs is its applicability to a number of similar situations, but a person is not a robot in which the program works according to a certain scheme established by specialists in the field of AI. The nature of a language is lively and varied, and the word meanings can easily change depending on the situation.

The polysemy of a language is explained by the limitation of the language signs. Romance, Germanic and Slavic languages have an expanded semantic structure, where the same word turns out to be multifunctional.

G.V. Kolshansky argues that "it is unthinkable to use any language unit without connection with other units or forms" (Kolshansky, 2010). A language begins to function only in the form of the interconnected words, couched in a communicative act and discourse.

According to I.A. Sternin: "the word meaning is the information carried by an individual word as a language unit, the mental content evoked by a word in the minds of native speakers."

It is possible to give a complete description of a word under study only by analyzing and summarizing all components of a discourse. This is the first method that allows you to get the actual meaning of a word. After summarizing all the elements of a discourse and analyzing the contexts, the meaning used can be called communicative. Such an analysis will reflect those meanings and semantic components that are currently communicatively relevant. This objective method of generalization, that is, in detachment from the mental component, forms the basis for the compilation of lexicographic dictionaries.

Let's move to studying the lexeme "Europe" in a variety of sources.

1. Geography. Modern Illustrated Encyclopedia, edit. by the Prof. A.P. Gorkin, 2006. According to the dictionary, "Europe is a part of the world, the western part of the Eurasian continent. Russia occupies a significant part of Eastern Europe. In addition, the following states are located in Europe: Austria, Albania, Andorra, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Vatican City, Great Britain, Hungary, Germany, Greece, Denmark, Ireland, Iceland, Spain, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Malta, Moldavia, Monaco, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, San Marino, Serbia and Montenegro, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine, Finland,

France, Croatia, Czech Republic, Switzerland, Sweden, Estonia, as well as the eastern part of Kazakhstan and a part of Türkiye.”

2. The Large Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language, edit. by Ph.D. S.A. Kuznetsov/ RAS, Institute for Linguistic Studies.

“EUROPE -s; f.

1. A part of the world that, together with Asia, makes up the Eurasia continent. Western, Eastern E.

2. pl.: Europe, Europ. colloq. about foreign countries,

about the countries of Western Europe. В европах побывал. Где уж нам, мы по европам не ездим! / I visited Europe. No matter what, we don't travel to Europe!

◇ Галопом по европам. Слишком быстро и бегло. Ну что ты мчишься галопом по европам! Разве можно так осматривать выставку?» / Galloping across Europe. Too fast and hastily. Well, why are you galloping across Europe?! What a thing to do! How can you take a tour of the exhibition like this?”

3. Russian National Corpus. The search word is Europe (Figure 1).

Fig.1. RNC search result for “Europe” query

We analyzed the first hundred proposed search results. The study included some of the proposed articles by means of random sampling.

– Migrant remittances are a factor of the innovative development of the global financial infrastructure // “Statistics Questions”, 2004: «**Европа** остается разделенной на национальные рынки, между которыми, помимо лингвистических, существуют различия в сфере налогового права и законов о защите прав потребителей» / “**Europe** remains divided into national markets, between which, apart from the linguistic ones, there are differences in the field of tax law and consumer protection laws” (Kommersant, No. 50 dated 22.03.2004). [Migrant remittances are a factor of the innovative development of the global financial infrastructure // “Statistics Questions”, 2004];

– Alexander Chudodeev. Schedule for Tomorrow (2003) // “Itogi”, 04.02.2003: «Ослабление доллара связано с тем, что экономика США находится в стадии рецессии и "просела" несколько больше, чем все ожидали, вот евро и вырвался так сильно вперед. Но **Европа** тоже находится в предкризисном состоянии, рецессии. Произошло более существенное, чем ранее планировалось, увеличение дефицита бюджета практически всех ведущих европейских стран. Просто сейчас у Америки негатива в экономике чуть больше, а у Европы – чуть меньше. Так что не думаю, что рост евро связан с более высокой ролью, которую эта

валюта, по мнению некоторых аналитиков, может играть в мировом экономическом устройстве» / “The weakening of the Dollar is related to the fact that the USA economy is in a recession stage and “has sank” somewhat more than everyone expected. That’s why the Euro has jumped so far ahead. But **Europe** is also in a pre-crisis state, a recession. There was a more significant rise in the budget deficit of almost all leading European countries than previously planned. It’s just that now America has a little more negativity in the economy, and Europe has a little less. So I don’t think that the growth of the Euro is related to a higher role that this currency, according to some analysts, can play in the global economic setup.”;

– Valery Kichin. Moscow near the Walls of Notre Dame (2002) // “Izvestia”, 21.05.2002: «– Вы родились в Сайгоне, ваш отец итальянец, мать француженка, а выросли в Риме – где ваш дом? – Мой дом – **Европа**. Я три года пробыл в Америке, но мне там жить не хочется. Мне необходим европейский, особенно латинский дух – равновесие между личным интересом и идеалом, чего в Америке нет. – Кто из композиторов вам близок, кого вы считаете учителями?» / – “You were born in Saigon, your father is Italian, your mother is French, and you grew up in Rome - where is your home? – My home is **Europe**. I spent three years in America, but I don’t want to live there. I need a European, especially a Latin spirit - a balance between a private interest and an ideal, which is not found in America. - “Which

composers are close to you, who do you consider to be your teachers?”;

- Elena Rotkevich. **Европа** устала обсуждать Калининград (2002) / Europe is tired of discussing Kaliningrad (2002) // “Izvestia”, 30.09.2002: «В понедельник в Петербурге открылась XI парламентская конференция Балтийского моря. На форум прибыло около 30 посланцев парламентов и парламентских организаций из 11 стран – соседей по Балтике, а также представители международных организаций – ПАСЕ, ОБСЕ. Главным вопросом стала проблема Калининграда» / “The XI Baltic Sea Parliamentary Conference has opened in St. Petersburg on Monday. About 30 envoys of parliaments and parliamentary organizations from 11 Baltic neighboring countries as well as the representatives of international organizations - PACE, OSCE, arrived at the forum. The main issue was the problem of Kaliningrad.”;

- “Kommersant Vlast” Magazine, 11.05.1999, “Washed Russia”: «Что, наконец, Америка подставила **Европу** и заметно ослабила ЕЭС, своего конкурента! Только один португальский репортер все это слушал с мрачной ухмылкой, глядя на меня удивленно: дошло до него! А расхлебывать всю эту войну, тащить на своем горбу всех этих беженцев (которых, заметим, ни Россия не берет, ни уж тем более Америка) будет **Европа**...» / “Well, finally, America has set **Europe** up and noticeably weakened the EEC, its competitor! Only one Portuguese reporter listened to all this with a gloomy grin, looking at me in surprise: He got it! And it will be **Europe** that will disentangle this whole war, putting up all these refugees (whom, we note, neither Russia, nor even America accept) on its shoulders...”;

- Davydov Yuri Vladimirovich, “Blue Tulips”: «Он вдруг увидел то, что давно видел Петр: Россия не **Европа** и не Азия, а часть света. Вот на этом-то и рехнулся математик. Он стал выбирать отечеству не европейский, не азиатский, не американский и даже не австралийский путь шествия, а совершенно оригинальный. Доктор Саблер нашел методу, иногда исцеляющую математиков-физиков-химиков» / “He suddenly saw what Peter had seen for a long time: Russia is not **Europe** or Asia, but a part of the world. This is where the mathematician went crazy. He began to choose for his motherland not a European, not an Asian, not an American, or even not an Australian way of procession, but a completely original one. Doctor Sabler has found a method that sometimes heals mathematicians, physicists, and chemists.”;

- Alexander Baunov, S.S. Sobyenin. Sergey Sobyenin: “Previously, cities fought for land and factories, but now – for people” (09.2017) // Daily Poster, 2017: «Собянин: Вы подняли важнейший вопрос развития мировых регионов: чем выше концентрация, тем выше производительность, тем больше ВВП страны; это работает как часы. Поэтому не совсем корректны сравнения с **Европой** – когда говорят о том, что там живут не в больших городах и не стремятся в большие города. Дело в том, что в **Европе** такая плотность населения, что вся **Европа** как один большой город» / “Sobyenin: You raised the most important issue of the development of the world regions: the higher the concentration, the higher the productivity, the greater the country’s GDP; it

runs like clockwork. Therefore, comparisons with **Europe** are not entirely correct - when they say that they do not live in big cities and do not strive to go to big cities. The point is that **Europe** has such a population density that the whole **Europe** is like one big city.”;

- Vasily Avchenko. Genealogy of Captain Vrungel. Vasily Avchenko on the 80th Anniversary of the Famous Sea Wolf (22.07.2017): «Пункт отправления вругелевской яхты «(По) беда» не назван, но, судя по всему, это Ленинград; дальше – **Европа**, Африка, Азия, Америка... / “The departure point of Vrungel’s “Victory” yacht has not been named, but, apparently, it is Leningrad; further – **Europe**, Africa, Asia, America...”;

- Ivan Martov, A.L. Dobrokhotov. «Постструктурализм – это в основном бредятина». Читательская биография философа Александра Доброхотова (22.02.2017): «Тогда как раз была эпоха диссоциации метафизической мысли, размывания ценностей: **Европа** в растерянности, Россия в растерянности, все относительно...» / “Poststructuralism is basically bullshit.” A reader’s biography of the philosopher Alexander Dobrokhotov (22.02.2017): “At that time there was just the epoch of the dissociation of a metaphysical thought, erosion of values: **Europe** is confused, Russia is confused, everything is relative...”;

- O. Volkova. Little by Little // “Ogonyok”, 2016: «В средневековой итальянской новелле говорится: «Женщина ничего не стоит, ежели не припахивает несвежей щукой». И уже гораздо позже появилось знаменитое письмо Наполеона Жозефине: «Не мойся! Еду!» Только в середине XIX века **Европа** всерьез озаботилась личной гигиеной населения. Появились труды парижанина Мишеля Леви, англичанина Эдмунда Паркса, предписывающие мыться, просто мыться, без колдовства и заклинаний. – На Руси изначально было совершенно другое отношение к гигиене, – говорит Екатерина Матанцева, создательница и генеральный директор компании, производящей натуральную косметику. – Давняя традиция бани у наших предков обусловлена тяжелым трудом в поле, когда вспотевшее тело облепляют мошки и комары» / “A medieval Italian novel says: “A woman is worth nothing if she doesn’t smell like a stale pike.” And much later, Napoleon’s famous letter to Josephine appeared: “Don’t wash yourself! I’m on my way!” Only in the middle of the XIX century **Europe** become seriously concerned about the personal hygiene of the population. The works of the Parisian Michel Levy and the Englishman Edmund Parkes appeared, prescribing to wash, just wash, without witchcraft or spells. – In Rus’, initially there was a completely different attitude towards the hygiene,” – according to Ekaterina Matantseva, a founder and CEO of a company producing natural cosmetics. – The long-standing tradition of the bathhouse among our ancestors stems from hard work in the field, when midges and mosquitoes cling to the sweaty body.”;

- L.A. Danilkin. Circular Detours through the Guts of a Beggar (2016): «Про то, что русским – даже «вменяемым» и вестернизированным – не стоит бежать в **Европу** с надеждой угнездиться в тамошнем разумном укладе:

иррациональность найдет их и там, и **Европа** не сможет их защитить» / “That’s about the fact that Russians – even “sane” and western-inspired ones – should not flee to **Europe** with the hope of nestling in the local rational way of life: irrationality will find them there too, and **Europe** will not be able to protect them.”;

– V. Surikov. Music of Oleg Menshikov Life // “Expert”, 2016: «Туда вошли все, вся **Европа** и Азия, причем на равных с американцами; все, кроме русских, или они там только на подхвате – как мои коллеги» / “Everyone entered there, all of **Europe** and Asia, and moreover, on equal terms with the Americans; everyone except the Russians, or they just hang around there - like my colleagues.”;

– “To stay away, forget, refuse: new and old recipes for Russia’s surrender (26.11.2016) // 2016”: «Между тем, отметим это обстоятельство, тема «Россия и **Европа**» в исторической части доклада рассмотрена на достаточно высоком уровне. Впрочем, и генерируемый в последнее время дискурс «Россия – это иная Европа» также не устраивает авторов доклада, поскольку не отвечает действительности и имеет, в конечном счете, в основе своей все тот же евроцентристский комплекс самой России. Стратегия стать частью Европы неосуществима. «Большая Европа» — это химера. «Настроения, которые можно выразить формулой «Россия — не **Европа**», возобладали, пожалуй, впервые в отечественной истории. Авторы доклада делают важную оговорку — признание факта, что «Россия — это не **Европа**» не означает, что «Россия по своей культуре и истории не перестанет быть во многом европейской страной». Авторы доклада пишут: «Европа и Россия могут быть добрыми соседями, и сформировать новую позитивную повестку взаимоотношений. Т. е. евроцентристские комплексы должна преодолеть не только Россия, но и сама **Европа** по отношению к ней. После того, как **Европа** подустанет от доминирующего сегодня дискурса «варвара у ворот», ей придется расширять свой дискурсивный репертуар в отношении России», – надеются они. / “Meanwhile, let us note this circumstance, the topic “Russia and **Europe**” in the historical part of the report is considered at a fairly high level. However, the recently generated discourse “Russia is the other Europe” is also not acceptable for the authors of the report, since it does not correspond to reality and is ultimately based on the same Eurocentric complex of Russia itself. The strategy of becoming a part of Europe is not feasible. “Greater Europe” is a chimera. “Sentiments that can be expressed by the formula “Russia is not **Europe**” prevailed, perhaps, for the first time in Russian history. The authors of the report make an important caveat - recognizing the fact that “Russia is not **Europe**” does not mean that “Russia, in its culture and history, will not cease to be a European country in many respects.” The authors of the report write: “Europe and Russia can be good neighbors and form a new positive agenda for relations. That is, not only Russia, but also **Europe** itself in relation to it must overcome Eurocentric complexes. Once **Europe** gets tired of the dominant “barbarian at the gates” discourse today, it will have to expand its discursive repertory in relation to Russia,” – they hope.;

– Sergey Kubrin. Pink Tank // Volga, 2015: «За Барсу болею всю жизнь, а гитару, на которой сейчас играл, из Мадрида привез. – И как там в Испании? – Лучше, чем здесь. Мне вообще **Европа** нравится, я туда свалить хочу. В **Европе** – жизнь. – А тут не жизнь? – Так уж вышло» / “I’ve been a Barca fan all my life, and I brought the guitar, I have been playing now, from Madrid. – How’s it going in Spain? - Better than here. In general, I like **Europe**, I want to run away there. There is life in **Europe**. - And isn’t this life here? - “It just happened that way.”;

– Fyodor Lukyanov. Stability for the Sake of Survival // Ogoniok, 2015: «Американское руководство после холодной войны и расширения НАТО на восток надеялось, что Старый Свет теперь сможет самостоятельно решать хотя бы собственные проблемы, однако раз за разом выясняется – будь то Балканы, Ближний Восток или единая валюта, – что **Европа** не в состоянии этого делать» / “The American leadership, after the Cold War and NATO expansion to the East, hoped that the Old World would now be able to independently solve at least its own problems, but time after time it turns out – whether it be the Balkans, the Middle East or a single currency - that **Europe** is not able to do this.” ;

– Peter Skorobogaty. Murder for Export // “Expert”, 2015: «Малайзийский «Боинг» рухнул в тот момент, когда военный конфликт сбавил обороты, а **Европа** начала задумываться о целесообразности санкций» / “Malaysian Boeing collapsed at the moment when the military conflict slowed down, and **Europe** began to think about the advisability of sanctions.”;

– Alexey Tarkhanov, Alexey Aslanyants, Dmitry Beglyarov. Paris (2015): «Если вы попались, то вырваться не удастся: контролеры отлично знают, что привод в полицию означает, что на ближайшие 5 лет **Европа** будет для вас закрыта» / “If you are caught, you will not be able to escape: the inspectors know very well that being brought to the police means that **Europe** will be closed for you for the next 5 years.”;

– What is going on there in Georgia? // “Russian Reporter”, 2015: «**Европа** молчит, США молчат, НАТО молчит, все истинно цивилизованные страны сделали вид, что ничего не было. Помощь предложили только Армения, Израиль, Россия и Украина» / “**Europe** keeps silent, the USA keeps silent, NATO keeps silent, all truly civilized countries pretended that nothing had happened. Only Armenia, Israel, Russia and Ukraine offered assistance.”;

– “Cowboys of Globalization.” Comments on the Article (10.2015): «**Европа** и США могут реализовать свою стратегию в инновационной области только тогда, когда мир будет достаточно богат, чтобы их интеллектуальные разработки стали достоянием всего человечества, превративших в востребованный продукт» / “**Europe** and the USA can implement their strategy in the innovation field only when the world is rich enough so that their intellectual developments become the Province of all Mankind, turning it into a sought-after product.”

Having analyzed the articles with the search lexeme “Europe”, presented by the Russian National Corpus, it should be concluded that in all publications the “Russia/Europe” antithesis can be traced, where the authors always contrast

Europe with Russia in political, cultural and everyday aspects. Thus, literary sources contain the concept of “Europe”, which in the thinking of Russian-speaking people is interpreted as its fixed second dictionary meaning (according to S.A. Kuznetsov’s dictionary): “About foreign countries, about the

countries of Western Europe.” In addition, Russian-speaking representatives usually call “Europe” those countries that have a higher standard of living, and where they strive to emigrate; as a rule, these countries are a part of the European Union or the Schengen area.

4) The Corpus of Contemporary American English – COCA. A search word is “Europe” (Figure 2).

Fig.2. Search page for the Corpus of Contemporary American English

Based on the search results, the English Language Corpus presented 80,658 texts (Figure 3), where a search word appears in the context. Let’s analyze some of them.

Fig.3. Search result of the Corpus of Contemporary American English for “Europe” query

– Putin «is considering the possibility of returning as president» — RT: «The Russian Prime Minister continued, saying that having freed **Europe** from Nazis, the Soviet people could not give it freedom, because they weren't free

themselves»¹.

– We need to talk. Left at the Lights: «I blog about issues occurring in **Europe** and European Parliament, and

¹ <http://rt.com/news/putin-president/>

how it affects domestic politics within the UK»².

– Check with Chip: Health Care Is Not a Right: «...they won't authorize a CAT scanner for our hospital – and besides the FDA prohibits the drug I should be prescribing, even though it is widely used in **Europe**, and the IRS might not allow the patient a tax deduction for it, anyhow, and I can't get a specialist's advice because the latest Medicare rules prohibit a consultation with this diagnosis»³.

– Popular Sports: Soccer And Basketball: The War Between The Two: «It's projected that within a few more years, the exposure of soccer in the United States, as well basketball in **Europe** and other countries...»⁴.

– An Interview with William Webster, CIA: «But aside from those, let's not forget we haven't left- the Soviet Union has not suddenly become kinder and gentler and all problems are over. Their troops are still in **Europe**. The strategic, modernized nuclear capability is still there»⁵.

– 48% of all the money spent on mobile - Android Authority: «For those who don't know, MediaTek makes chips that are usually found in budget smartphones meant for the Chinese, Indian, and Russian markets. It's damn near impossible to find a phone in **Europe** or America using a MediaTek chip because of the intellectual property issues. That's not to say MediaTek's chips are bad; without them there wouldn't be \$100 Android phones»⁶.

– US needs Ukraine priorities straight - Global Public Square - CNN.com: «President Victor Yanukovich says he aims to balance Ukraine's ties between Russia and **Europe**, with EU integration as a 'strategic aim'»⁷.

– Discuss, Debate: Obama's Second Term - New Rochelle, NY Patch: «Beyond this little corner of the world we have **Russia**, China, **Europe** and other, much more important connections to keep up with»⁸.

– World hunger: the problem left behind: « Huge swathes of Russia and Eastern **Europe**, African countries like Angola, Southern Sudan etc. sit on fertile land that is underutilized, and primed for an economic solution

– House OKs bill normalizing trade with Russia | The Journal Gazette: «The vote to establish permanent normal trade relations was a priority for American businesses concerned that they were being left behind as **Europe** and China **move into Russia** is market of 140 million consumers»⁹.

Having analyzed a variety of materials offered by the Corpora, the conclusion follows that among native English speakers, “Russia” and “Europe” concepts are contrasted in the same way as in the Russian-speaking environment. In addition, English speakers most often use the word “Europe” to designate those countries on which the most important political decisions

in the international arena depend, and which are capable of influencing other states, for example, Germany, France and Great Britain.

Thus, the lexeme “Europe” in Russian and foreign sources is equally opposed to Russia and includes the most influential countries that have a high level of political significance in the international arena and are characterized by a high standard of living.

Question 2. Which countries are united by the lexeme “Europe” among Russian speakers, and are they opposed to each other?

Based on the analysis of the texts examined in the first question, it should be noted that Russian speakers in the term “Europe” most often include those countries that for many years have been considered in Russian society as “the standard of a better life, accessible only to representatives of the establishment.” These are those countries that have a high level of immigration due to the attractiveness of living in it according to various criteria. These countries are Germany, Italy and France. Political texts designate as “Europe” those countries that have the greatest influence in the international arena, for example, Great Britain, Germany, France, Italy, Spain and Switzerland.

In the linguistic environment of Russian speakers, there are well-established words and phrases associated with Europe:

a) «галопом по европам» / “galloping across Europe” is a phraseological unit that came into use after the travel essays of the poet A.A. Zharov based on the results of a trip to Western Europe. On his return, Alexander Zharov published notes about the trip in the Komsomolskaya Pravda newspaper. In the issues of February 14 and 16 and March 1, 1928, the travel essays entitled “Gallop across Europe” were published, which were harshly criticized by Maxim Gorky, reproaching travelers (including A.A. Zharov) for a superficial point of view of foreign countries and careless handling of facts. Soon this phrase was caught up by other literary men and writers. Now this expression means a fast acquaintance with something, a cursory and shallow observation, a superficial judgment about something without delving into the essence;

b) «Пустите Дуньку в Европу!» / “Let Dunka go to Europe!” is a phrase that became a phraseological unit from the work “Lyubov Yarovaya” by K.A. Trennev. The professor’s cook Dunka makes an attempt to emigrate, and this is the reason why the Professor Gornostaev ironically pronounces this phrase about an enthusiastic attitude towards life in foreign European countries;

² <http://samambreen.wordpress.com/2012/10/21/we-need-to-talk/>

³ <http://checkwithchip.blogspot.com/2012/11/health-care-is-not-right.html>

⁴ <http://bikesolidarias.blogspot.com/2012/10/soccer-and-basketball-war-between-two.html>

⁵ ABC_Nightline, 1990

⁶ <http://www.androidauthority.com/qualcomm-dominates-chip-market-120658/>

⁷

<http://globalpublicsquare.blogs.cnn.com/2012/09/28/u-s-needs-ukraine-priorities-straight/>

⁸ <http://newrochelle.patch.com/articles/discuss-debate-obama-s-second-term>

⁹

<http://www.journalgazette.net/article/20121117/NEWS04/311179929-1/NEWS09>

с) «прорубить окно в Европу» / “to open a window to Europe” is a phrase that has become known to any Russian schoolchild when reading the literary work “The Bronze Horseman” by A.S. Pushkin, where the founding of St. Petersburg City by Peter the Great, which became a Russian port on the Baltic Sea, through which one could get to Europe, is called as “window to Europe”.

Thus, the Russia/Europe opposition developed historically in the Russian-speaking space, both in culture and in everyday life, politics and religion.

Question 3. What is the semantic content of the phrase from a will “exclusively in relation to the property located in Europe”, based on the interpretation of the lexeme “Europe” in various Russian and foreign sources as well as based on the generally accepted usage among native speakers of Russian?

For the most accurate interpretation of controversial phrases and expressions that are the subjects of linguistic research, forensic linguists examine both the literal interpretation of phrases, which is enshrined in various scientific manuals and dictionaries, and the extralinguistic context, polysemy and presupposition - everything that makes up the background thesaurus.

In fact, according to psycholinguistic theory, the most significant thing, in addition to the linguistic meaning of the text, is the identification of extra-linguistic meaning. That is, a forensic linguist needs to identify the specific meaning that a specific author put into a word, with an individual set of characteristics formed under the influence of an author’s life experience.

Accordingly, to identify this individual meaning, not only linguistic, but also extra-linguistic knowledge about an author, who used a word or a phrase under study, are required. It is necessary to take into account many different factors that preceded the speech situation, namely: a level of education, social circle, joining various communities, visiting other countries, etc.

The above factors constitute the so-called background knowledge, which is directly related to the statement context and is an important source for the verbalization of thoughts. Thus, background knowledge is defined as a set of information of a cultural and material-historical, geographical and pragmatic nature that is assumed to be possessed by a native speaker of a given language. Background knowledge helps decipher the relevant context.

CONCLUSION

In the object presented in the study, a testator used a phrase, which in the approved translation from Italian is fixed as: “... declares that he has the final and conscious intention to dispose of the inheritance of his property after his death, exclusively in relation to the property located in Europe...”

According to the Large Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language by S.A. Kuznetsov, the lexeme “exclusively”, used in the phrase under study, is a particle that

is equated to the particles “only”, “just”, “merely”:

Thus, the testator K., in the will, presented for the study, intends to dispose only of the property located in Europe. The inclusion of this particle “exclusively” in the specified phrase at the pragmatic level indicates one of two circumstances:

a) The testator K. had property in other geographical parts of the world, except Europe (Asia, Africa, Australia, America, Antarctica), therefore, in this will he wishes to dispose of the property located only in Europe, and in this case he does not wish to dispose of property located in other parts of the world, or

b) The testator K., being a citizen of Russia, has preliminary knowledge (presupposition) that “Europe is not Russia” (See Questions 1 and 2), and, based on this knowledge, forms a phrase presented for the study where in this will he has a desire to dispose of the property located in International Europe, but in this case he does not want to dispose of the property located in Russia.

If the testator K. believed that Russia is also Europe, like Italy, the phrase contained in the will would be absurd. But introducing the particle “exclusively” definitely introduces the choice of one country.

As part of this study, an author conducted a survey of colleagues with higher education, whose age ranged from 30-55 years; the number of respondents was 37 people. The respondents did not have information about the case; the question was posed to them like this:

“For which countries do you use the term “Europe” to designate?”

Answer options:

1. To designate the countries of the European Union (Germany, Italy, Austria, Spain, Switzerland, France, etc.);
2. To designate Europe as a geographical continent, including both the European Union and Russia, Belarus, Ukraine, Croatia.”

According to the survey results, 68% of respondents chose the option No. 1, 32% of them voted for the second option. Thus, the public opinion survey confirmed the result of the study carried out above. An author’s colleagues use the word “Europe” in a context that is opposed to Russia, that is, in the thinking of the majority of respondents, - “Russia is not Europe.”

It should be noted that a testator owned the property on the right of ownership exclusively on the territory of Italy and Russia, and thus, in our opinion, the will of a testator was to dispose of the property which is located in Italy for the children from his first marriage.

Currently, we see that the professionalism of lexicographers and the hundreds of dictionaries they created fade into insignificance, but, nevertheless, remain an important source of knowledge. Other objective data about the use of the language units by a specific person in a specific discourse come to the fore.

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